

Effects of EMS on some characters of selected M₂ plants, Chinsurah, India.

Selection	Duration (d)	Height (cm)	Panicle no.	Panicle length (cm)	Grain size		Grain shape (L:B)	1000-grain wt (g)	Aroma
					Length (mm)	Breadth (mm)			
Control	152	156	8	24	6.0	2.2	2.7	13.0	Present
CNM-RDP-42	120	100	8	16	5.5	2.8	2.0	12.5	Present
CNM-RDP-39	118	134	9	26	7.4	2.7	2.7	18.1	Present
CNM-RDP-41	136	133	6	24	7.2	2.5	2.9	16.0	Absent
CNM-RDP-46	124	19	7	20	7.8	2.5	3.1	16.5	Absent
CNM-RDP-48	139	133	6	24	7.5	2.5	3.0	16.5	Absent
CNM-RDP-35	134	100	7	21	8.8	3.0	2.6	22.3	Present
CNM-RDP-36	119	85	9	23	9.5	2.8	3.3	25.1	Absent
CNM-RDP-38	124	114	8	26	8.9	2.8	3.1	22.4	Absent
CNM-RDP-37	123	134	10	24	9.5	2.7	3.4	19.8	Present
CNM-RDP-40	120	110	9	26	8.9	2.1	4.2	15.1	Absent
CNM-RDP-43	120	103	8	26	9.3	2.0	4.5	17.6	Absent
CNM-RDP-49	137	138	6	26	9.2	2.1	4.3	17.0	Absent
CNM-RDP-50	127	81	11	21	8.9	2.2	3.9	17.5	Present

Randhunipagal seeds to EMS at 0.25, 0.50, 0.75, and 1% concentrations for 24 h to cause mutation and develop a dwarf, aromatic, long-slender grained line, and to quantify optimum EMS dosage for this purpose.

The M₁ was grown in 1977 kharif and the M₂ in 1978. Mutation rate was

highest at 0.25% concentration, followed by 0.50%. None of the M₁ produced seeds at EMS concentrations higher than 0.50%. This may be caused by mutagenic effects at higher doses that involve many genes and lead to spikelet sterility and plant death.

Morphological and grain type mutants

were studied in the M₂. All mutants matured earlier than the control. Plant height, panicle number and length, grain size and shape, and grain weight differed substantially from those of the control (see table). Some nonaromatic mutants were obtained. Largest variation was in grain shape and weight. *ℒ*

IR36 for rainfed conditions in Madhya Pradesh, India

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IR36 is a semidwarf rice with long, slender, translucent grains and good

cooking quality. It matures in 120 d and is tolerant of gall midge and bacterial leaf blight.

In Madhya Pradesh, 80% of rice is grown in rainfed fields. IR36 performed well in multilocation tests (see table), and has become popular in areas where rainfall begins the 3d wk of Jun and continues through mid-Sep. *ℒ*

Promising new rice varieties for late kharif in the Cauvery Command Area, Karnataka, India

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Low temperatures during reproductive phase and stem borer incidence limit late kharif (Sep) rice in the Cauvery Command Area. In 1983, the All India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project at Mandya identified several short-duration, high yielding, stem borer

Grain yield of IR36 in rainfed areas of Madhya Pradesh.

Variety	Grain yield ^a (t/ha)						Mean
	Raipur	Jabalpur	Waraseoni	Bagwai	Rewa	Jagdulpur	
<i>1978</i>							
IR36	4.3	4.0	5.4*	4.2*	6.2*	-	4.8
Rasi	3.4	3.7	4.5	3.4	4.9	-	4.0
Ratna	3.5	3.8	4.5	3.8	4.9	-	4.1
<i>1980</i>							
IR36	0.6	2.4	4.1*	-	3.8	-	2.7
Abha	0.9	2.2	3.3	-	3.3	-	2.5
<i>1982</i>							
IR36	3.2	3.4	3.7	3.7	2.3	5.0	3.5
Anupama	2.9	3.7	3.5	4.0	3.4	4.7	3.7
<i>1983</i>							
IR36	2.9*	2.1	-	2.9	3.1*	-	-
Anupama	3.0	3.1	-	2.1	2.7	-	-
Deepti	2.1	2.8	-	3.1	2.6	-	-

^a The asterisk (*) means that IR36 was superior to Ratna in 1978, to Abha in 1980, and to Deepti in 1983.

Performance of stem borer-resistant, late kharif varieties, Karnataka, India.

Variety	Days to 50% flowering	Grain yield (t/ha)	Whiteheads (%)
IET7633	109	3.2	10
IET7614	102	3.0	7
IET7261	102	2.8	8
IET7617	85	1.4	30
Mangala	94	2.3	18
CD (0.05)	-	11.7	7

resistant varieties as possible replacements for locally grown Mangala

(see table). The most promising varieties were IET7633 and IET7614, both of

Rasi Finegora, and IET7261 from Rasi Mettasamma. *ℳ*

BG367-4, a promising short-duration rice

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BG3674 (BG280-12/PTB 33) is a promising short-duration rice received through the International Rice Testing

Program. It was evaluated at PES in the 1980 International Rice Observational Nursery (IRON), and performed well in 1980-84 in Jun-Sep.

BG367-4 yielded 9.5 t ha in 1983, with average yields of 6.5 t ha over 4 yr. It yielded 25% more than TKM9 and 35% more than ADT36 (see table). Duration ranged from 109 to 115 d, averaging 112 d.

BG3674 has semidwarf (91 cm)

stature, long slender grains, and white rice. The 1,000-grain weight is 23.4 g.

Yield potential is high because of high panicle weight (1.33 g).

The variety has been nominated for the 1985-86 Rice Coordinated Yield Trial-2 (100-120 d) at Tamil Nadu Agricultural University experiment stations and is being used as a donor in the PES hybridization program. *ℳ*

Performance of BG367-4 at Ambasamudram, India, 1980-84.

Variety	Grain yield (t/ha)						Flowering time (d)	Plant ht (cm)	Panicles/hill	1000-grain wt (g)	Panicle wt (g)
	IRON 1980	Yield trial 1981	Yield trial 1982	IRYN (VE) 1983	Yield trial 1984	IRYN (VE) 1984					
BG3674	6.9	5.5	5.1	9.5	6.1	6.1	82	91	8.3	23.4	1.33
ADT36	5.1	4.4	5.2	—	4.1	5.4	84	84	8.9	24.2	1.16
TKM9	—	5.0	5.3	6.6	4.3	4.6	82	82	8.2	24.5	1.27
m + σ	6.9	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
CD (P = 0.05)	—	1.1	0.5	1.4	0.1	1.3	—	—	—	—	—

Evaluation of six rice genotypes in relation to field hydrology

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We evaluated the effect of drought on yield of six rices with different durations in 1983 wet and 1984 semiwet seasons.

In both seasons, the rices were planted on 7 Sep and grown with similar agronomic practices. Weekly precipitation, evaporation, daily groundwater level, and flowering time were recorded (Fig. 1). Drought was longer and more severe in semiwet season. Evaporation exceeded precipitation 11 wk after seeding in semiwet season and after 16 wk in wet season. In semiwet season, groundwater level was below 80 cm 12 wk after seeding.

Short-duration MW 10 performed best in semiwet season, yielding 2.5 t/ha. Late-maturing Mahsuri yielded lowest, 0.3 t/ha. Poorva, IR36, Usha, and Safri 17 produced intermediate yields. Safri 17

Water table depth (cm)

Weekly evaporation and rainfall (mm)

1. Weekly precipitation, evaporation, daily groundwater level, and flowering time of 6 genotypes. Kaipur, India